

Automated RSMM

This file includes additional details of the automated RSMM framework.

Table 1: RSMM practices and metadata mapping: Practices of the focus area, **Software Project Management** is presented in this figure and mapped to metadata. The methods used to identify the practices from the metadata are shown in the heatmap, indicated by the letters K (keyword based search), X (presence of metadata files), F (Mining GitHub fields), and A (Analysis of GitHub activities).

1 Case study projects

Our current study covers 8 case projects. This section provides a brief description of them.

Table 2: Case studies software and their description

Software	Software full name	Description
BridgeDb Java [15]		a library that maps identifiers from one source to another. For example, it can map NCBI Gene identifiers to ensemble gene identifiers and DOIs to PubMed identifiers.

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Software	Software full name	Description
Kernel tuner [16]		simplifies the development of highly optimised and auto-tuned CUDA, OpenCL, and C code, supporting many advanced use-cases and optimisation strategies that speed up the auto-tuning process.
DIANNA [17]	Deep Insight And Neural Network Analysis	a Python package that brings explainable AI (XAI) to the research project. It wraps carefully selected XAI methods in a simple, uniform interface.
3D Slicer [18]		a free, open-source software for visualisation, processing, segmentation, registration, and analysis of medical, biomedical, and other 3D images and meshes; and planning and navigating image-guided procedures.
OceanParcels [19]	Ocean Probably A Really Computationally Efficient Lagrangian Simulator	project develops Parcels, a set of Python classes and methods to create customisable particle tracking simulations using output from Ocean Circulation models. Parcels can track passive and active particulates such as water, plankton, plastic and fish.
Haddock3 [20]	High Ambiguity Driven protein-protein DOCKing	a modular software for the integrative modelling and refinement of biomolecular complexes.
eWaterCycle [21]		package makes it easier to use hydrological models without having intimate knowledge about how to install and run the models.
Eclipse SUMO [22]	Eclipse Simulation of Urban MObility	an open-source, highly portable, microscopic and continuous traffic simulation package that handles large networks. It allows for intermodal simulation, including pedestrians, and comes with a large set of tools for scenario creation.

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